

EXAMINING THE EFFECT OF ISLAMIC WORK VALUE ON A COMMITMENT TO CUSTOMER SUPERIOR VALUE: THE ROLE OF TRUST IN MANAGER AND UNETHICAL BEHAVIOR

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Abstract

This study shed a light on the Islamic work value include piety (taqwa), benevolence (ihsan), and patient (sabar) directly affect commitment to customer superior value. Moreover, it examines the relationship between Islamic work value and commitment to customer superior value through trust in manager and unethical behavior. Totally 115 salespeople of Islamic Micro Finance in Central Java Province, Indonesia have been selected as a sample. This study analyzes the data using a two-step approach namely confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and structural equation modelling (SEM). The results demonstrate that Islamic work value positively and significantly affects commitment to customer superior value. Likewise, Islamic work value affects trust in manager and, in turn, trust in manager impacts commitment to customer superior value. Finally, this study confirms that Islamic work value has a negative and significant effect on employee unethical behavior, however, this study fails to relate unethical behavior to commitment to customer superior value. This study discusses the results, offers managerial implications, and informs the limitation as well as recommendations for future study.

Keywords: Islamic work value, trust in manager, unethical behavior, commitment to customer superior value.

1. INTRODUCTION

The enlargement of the Muslim population in the world that continuously increases support the progress of halal business (Battour & Ismail, 2016). Shafaei and Mohamed (2015) reported that Muslim people have achieved 30 percent of the whole inhabitants, and this presentation will increase constantly. Consequently, the Muslim market segment is developing rapidly with special characteristics at the global level as well as the improvement of standard living of many Islamic countries (Hodge, 2005). According to the recent news, the report of Global Islamic Economy 2021 informed that Muslim spending in the world is estimated to achieve USD 2.4 trillion (Safira & Purnama, 2021). The phenomena of the rapid growth of global halal business and the prospect of the Muslim market attracted this study to explore Muslim employee

behavior in Indonesia as the biggest Muslim population, focusing on Islamic work value and commitment to customer superior value

The increasing numbers of Muslim people who intend to implement every activity based on Islamic religion have consequences on a significant amount of study that adapted various themes such as Sharia bank, halal business, Muslim employee behavior etc. Moreover, the importance of religion as a basis of values and become acceptable for the people in the world, achieve three-quarters who believe in religion (Zuckerman, 2005). Previous studies have explored several topics related to the effect of religion on values. Furthermore, value has become the principle that guides human behaviour and religion affects values related to conveying values and ethics and in turn religious value orientation strengthly support religious behavior (Arslan, 2001; Cukur, De Guzman, & Carlo, 2004). Previous studies focusing on Islamic management informed that Islamic work value has been included as the pillar of studies (Wahab & Masron, 2020). Although values have become a popular topic in global research, previous studies elucidating work value from Islamic sources are relatively unexplored.

A few numbers of scholars have related Islamic spirituality and work attitude and behavior in various contexts, for instance, Hamzah, Hamzah, Othman, and Devi (2016) clarified the effect of Islamic values on Muslim women leadership style. Moreover, Wahab, Quazi, and Blackman (2016) have measured and validated Islamic work values in the empirical study include trustworthiness responsibility, benevolence, fairness, honesty etc. Another study conducted by Wahab (2017) investigated the influence of religious work value on sustainable work behavior, and sustainable energy consumption. Employing the theory of planned behavior, Rehan, Block, and Fisch (2019) elucidated Islamic values and practices affect entrepreneurship intentions. More recent studies verified the Islamic work ethics to predict employee response to change (Al-Shamali, Irani, Haffar, Al-Shamali, & Al-Shamali, 2021). A current study conducted by Sani and Ekowati (2021) investigated organizational commitment, marketing strategy, and organizational citizenship behavior includes Islamic spirituality, spirituality at work and Islamic corporate social responsibility. Although the previous studies have investigated Islamic religion and work attitude and behavior, they rarely explored how Islamic work values affect employee commitment to customer superior value. Therefore, this study attempts to examine the Islamic work value affects employee commitment to customer superior value through trust in manager and unethical behavior to fill the research gap.

This study would like to contribute to the crucial aspects of employee behavior theory based on the Islamic perspective considering several aspects. First, the theme of halal business has a considerable amount of development; however, the studies focusing on commitment customer superior value in halal business are scant. Second, Previous studies rarely explored trust in manager and employee unethical behavior from the Islamic perspective. Third, only a few numbers of scholars have examined Islamic work values and they never look out for the role of trust in managers and unethical behavior in achieving commitment to superior customer value. In particular, this study aims to investigate the effect of Islamic work value on commitment to customer superior value. Moreover, it verifies the influence of Islamic work value on trust in manager and, in turn trust, in manager affects commitment to customer

superior value. Finally, this framework examines the effect of Islamic work value on unethical behavior and subsequently, the effect of unethical behavior on commitment to customer superior value. Lastly, this study discusses the results, suggest some management implications, inform the limitation of the research and recommend for future investigation.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

2.1. Literature review

2.1.1 Islamic Work Value

Islamic work value refers to the conception of appropriate benefits or qualities based on Islamic teaching in the Qur'an and hadith. Scholars have described that the Islamic perspective covered every single behavior of life that every performance is based on religious orientation (Ismail, Saad, Badron, Hashim, & Abdullah, 2012). Scholars have included different elements in Islamic work values such as responsibility, patience, hardworking, honesty, kindness, good conduct, the persistence as well as punctuality (Abdullah, Omar, Rahman, & Adham, 2013). The study conducted by Khadijah, Kamaluddin, and Salin (2015) also informed responsibility, hardworking, honesty, justice, truthfulness, and competitiveness are a part of Islamic work values. While, Furqani (2015) has identified that Islamic work value only includes three elements namely responsibility, piety, and justice. Some scholars have defined Islamic work value in various ways and they have included all the items in Islamic work value which have a positive aspect to be adapted to enhance a better leadership or employee performance.

2.1.2 Commitment To Superior Customer Value

Building an employee who commit to deliver superior customer value will stimulate positive customer behaviors remains a significant challenge for most companies. Moreover, perceived value refers to the confirmation between the customer benefit and sacrifices such as the cost they have spent and the expectation of their needs and wants (Lapierre, 2000). Value-based selling includes three crucial elements: first, systematically customers' business purposes, second, improving an offering to help customers in achieving the goals, and third, credibly presenting how the offering can support the business customer's profit (Terho, Haas, Eggert, & Ulaga, 2012). In the process of customer-employee communications, the involvement of customers can become a key factor influencer that enhances customer valuable experiences (Locander, White, & Newman, 2020; Prebensen, Woo, Chen, & Uysal, 2012). Moreover, customer involvement also determines the delivery of service and customer value perception (Mustak, 2019). Schwepker Jr (2013) defines a commitment to superior customer value as the personal power to provide superior value to the customer and involves an individual, affective commitment to increase the value of the customer.

2.1.3 Trust In Manager

Employee trust in manager is considering an important factor in affecting unethical behaviour and some antecedents of trust in managers are caused by individual factors and social factors. The definition of trust in manager denotes the level to which the employee believes in the

manager's justice and integrity (Scott B. MacKenzie, Philip M. Podsakoff, & Gregory A. Rich, 2001). The manager who treats the employee with fairness can enhance the employee belief, like and trust in their manager (Alexander & Ruderman, 1987; Dwyer, Schurr, & Oh, 1987; Flaherty & Pappas, 2000; Folger & Konovsky, 1989; Konovsky & Pugh, 1994; Lind & Tyler, 1988).

2.1.4 Unethical Behavior

Jones (1991) described corporate scandals and incidents of the employee involving in unethical or illegal and immoral behavior to the society stimulate scholar's attractiveness to the characteristics and reason of this unethical behaviour in a company. It was informed that stealing, cheating customers, and misrepresenting performance are some examples categorized employee unethical behavior (Linda Klebe Treviño, Niki A. Den Nieuwenboer, & Jennifer J. Kish-Gephart, 2014). This study further supports in reducing unethical behaviour by presenting the Islamic work value happening in the salesperson that helps unethical intention such as intention to commit in performing behaviour that reflected to tumble outside of what is ethically acceptable with their occupation.

2.2. Hypotheses Development

2.2.1 Islamic Work Value And Commitment To Customer Superior Value

The effect of Islamic work value on employee commitment to customer superior value was rarely explored in the previous studies, however, some evidence has guided this indication. Ahmed (2010) explain the example of a Muslim country, the company has declared on halal business and other activities that allowed by Islamic teaching to perform responsibility towards God and stakeholders, employees and customers. One factor of Islamic work value, for instance, piety denotes the devout performance of religious commitment based on Islamic instruction and as the value to distinguish between a Muslim and other Muslim. Previous studies informed that piety leads to people perform actively considering integrity and justice (Beekun & Badawi, 1999; Mukred Mohsen, 2007). It is also informed that Islamic work value such as benevolence motivates Muslim to perform an extra role behavior as an act of generosity (Al-Ghazali, 2008). Therefore, the above discussion leads to the following hypothesis.

H1. Islamic work value positively and significantly affects commitment to customer superior value.

2.2.2 Islamic Work Value And Trust In Manager

Trust in manager refers to the level to which the employee believes in the fairness and integrity of the manager (Scott B MacKenzie, Philip M Podsakoff, & Gregory A Rich, 2001). Previous studies have seldom explored the relationship between Islamic work value and trust in manager, however, some guidance from prior researchers can see this relationship. Mayer, Davis, and Schoorman (1995) purposed their research model related to the antecedents and outcome of organizational trust and offering several propositions of the antecedents of trust such as ability, benevolence, and integrity. Another study conducted by Sirdeshmukh, Singh, and Sabol (2002) reported that operational competence, operational benevolence, and problem-

solving orientation positively affect trust in frontline employee behaviour, therefore, this study offering the following hypotheses.

H2. Islamic work value positively and significantly affects trust in manager.

2.2.3 Trust In Manager And Commitment To Customer Superior Value.

Some prior studies have resulted in the positive effect of trust in the manager on affective organization commitment (Camgöz & Karapinar, 2016; Velez, Sanchez, Florez, & Alvarez-Dartet, 2015). Moreover, the quality of the relationship between salespeople and sales managers has been reported that salespeople's commitment impacts positively on superior customer value (Schwepker Jr, 2017). High quality of a correlation occurs when the partners in an exchange achieve mutual relationships (Liden, Sparrowe, & Wayne, 1997). A recent study conducted by Schwepker Jr (2019) demonstrated that trust in managers positively affects salespeople commitment to superior customer value, therefore, this study offers the following hypothesis.

H3. Trust in manager positively and significantly affects commitment to customer superior value.

2.2.4 Islamic Work Values And Employee Unethical Behavior.

Unethical employee behaviour includes thieving from the company, cheating customers, and manipulating performance (Linda Klebe Treviño, Niki A Den Nieuwenboer, & Jennifer J Kish-Gephart, 2014). Previous researches focusing on ethical decision making described that management affects ethical behaviour in a company such as integrity, concern, and benevolence (Ferrell & Gresham, 1985; Jones, 1991). Several literatures have identified the antecedents of unethical behavior includes personal characteristics and morality in the company context (Brown & Treviño, 2014; Kish-Gephart, Harrison, & Treviño, 2010). Focusing on Islamic working value, a previous study conducted by Mukred Mohsen (2007) explained that although piety as a part of Islamic work value is a core of personal value can be identified from the behavior of Muslims when they perform their behavior. Moreover, piety as one of the elements of Islamic work value would lead to people to behave proactively and to occupy morality and fairness performance (Beekun & Badawi, 1999; Mukred Mohsen, 2007), logically Islamic work value will reduce unethical behavior, and consequently, the following hypothesis is purposed.

H4. Islamic work value negatively and significantly affects employee unethical behaviour.

2.2.5 Employee Unethical Behavior And Commitment To Customer Superior Value.

Scholars have empirically presented in their studies that customer-oriented selling has a negative effect on unethical behavior intention (Schwepker & Schultz, 2013). In addition, customer-oriented selling also reduce employees to act unethical behaviour (Howe, Hoffman, & Hardigree, 1994). Schwepker Jr (2017) informed that commitment increase salesperson to perform superior customer value and reduce unethical intention. A recent study from Schwepker Jr (2019) reported that a salesperson commitment to perform superior customer

value negatively affects the salesperson's unethical intention, therefore this study purposes the following hypothesis.

H5. Employee unethical behaviour positively and significantly affects commitment to customer superior value.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Research Framework

This framework elucidates work value from the perspective of Islamic religion namely Islamic work value as second-order consist of piety, benevolence, and patient. First, it investigates the effect of Islamic work value directly affects commitment to customer superior value. Second, this study identifies the influence of Islamic work value on trust in manager and the subsequent of trust in manager impacts commitment to customer superior value. Lastly, this framework investigates the effect of Islamic work value on unethical behavior and in turn, unethical behavior affects commitment to customer superior value. Figure 1 depicts any detail of the research framework.

Figure 1: A proposed model of Islamic work value and commitment to superior customer value.

3.2. Sample And Data Collection

This study collects the data through a survey using questionnaires distributed to salespeople of Islamic microfinance in Central Java Province. All salespeople of the Islamic microfinance in Central Java Province will be identified based on the statistic of Bank Indonesia as the population. Then, this study chooses the salespeople employing the proportional random sampling methods based on the area divided by four areas (South, north, west and east area of Central Java Province).

This study employs a pilot test to examine the reliability of the questionnaires to avoid response bias from the respondents. Approximately, 50 salespersons as the respondents of the Islamic microfinance institution in Central Java Province have been evaluated to fill out the pilot test focusing on Islamic work value and commitment to customer superior value. The result showed that the value of Cronbach alpha of each construct namely Islamic work value, trust in manager, unethical behavior and commitment to customer superior value exceeds .70 and the value of KMO-MSA above 60, indicating the validity and reliability. The next step, this study come to the real survey involving fifteen students to distribute the questionnaires and collect data supervised by one junior lecturer. The survey employed Google Forms and was sent via WhatsApp, Facebook, Instagram, and email. The survey distributes approximately 200 questionnaires from June until December 2020 to the salespeople of Islamic microfinance proportionally based on the area and each area receives 125 questionnaires. Totally 115 respondents participated in this survey with a response rate of 57.5 % continue to be analyzed after selecting the complete data.

3.3. Measure

The investigation of this study employs questionnaires based on the previous studies that established used as a measurement scale. The response of the respondents is available on the Likert scale from strongly disagree represented by number 1 to strongly agree represented by number 7. The measurement scale of Islamic work value as second-order includes piety (taqwa), benevolence (ihsan), and patient (sabr) were adapted from the previous study conducted by Wahab et al. (2016). Hence trust in the manager was modified from Schwepker and Schultz (2013) and employee unethical behaviour was borrowed from Harris and Ogbonna (2002). The remain construct namely commitment to customer superior value was extracted from Scott B MacKenzie et al. (2001).

All of the questions in the questionnaires will be translated into the Indonesian language to make the respondents understand the items easily. The translation from English into the Indonesian language was consulted by three doctoral scholars who have an expert and competency in these two languages, therefore, the results of the translation of the questionnaires are appropriate and represent the meaning of the construct. Table 1 displays the item scale of each construct and the value of cronbach alpha.

Table 1: Item-scale of each construct

Dimension	Measurement	Cronbach alpha
Islamic Work Value	I am very strict about following my religious belief.	.802
	I am influenced by my consciousness about God when doing my work.	
	Even though my performance is good, I always strive to perform better	
	I often put in extra effort in my work.	
	Fear of punishment causes me to be on the right track. (R)	
Trust in Manager	When perplexed by a difficulty, I am able to keep my patience easily.	.858
	I feel quite confident that my supervising manager will always try to treat me fairly.	
	My supervising manager would never try to gain an advantage by deceiving his or her sales representatives	
Unethical Behaviour	I have complete faith in the integrity of my supervising manager.	.918
	Sometimes, people here "get at customers" to make the rest of us laugh.	
	People here never show off in front of customers. (R)	
Commitment to Customer Superior Value	Sometimes, when customers aren't looking, people here deliberately mess things up	.870
	I completely understand the importance of providing superior value to our customers.	
	I often discuss customer value-related issues with people outside of my organization.	
	Providing superior value to our customers should be the number one priority of my organization.	

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. RESULTS

4.1.1 Descriptive Statistics

This study describes the socio-demographic profile of the respondents include gender, age, marital status, educational background, monthly household income, and working experience. The respondents participated in this survey 75% were male and the remains female respondent was 25%. The majority of the respondents were between 31-40 years old that achieved 43%, followed by 20-30 years old (31%) and 41-50 years old (22%). The single respondents reach 76%, while the other 24% were married. The first rank of the participants in this survey had undergraduate education background (69.6%) and was followed by a master (25.2%) with the majority received less than IDR 5.000.000 monthly income (41.7%) and between IDR 5.000.000 and IDR 7.500.000 (20.0%). The Majority of the participants have been working in

Islamic microfinance institutions for more than 6 years (60%) and less than 2 years (18.2%). Any details of the respondents' socio-demographic profile are described in table 2.

Table 2: Socio-demographic profile of the respondents

		N	Percentage (%)	Cumulative Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	87	75.0	75.0
	Female	28	25.0	100.0
Age	20~30 years old	36	31.0	31.0
	31~40 years old	50	43.0	74.0
	41~50 years old	25	22.0	96
	51- 60 years old	3	2.6	98.6
	>60 years old	1	1.4	100.0
Marital Status	Single	88	76.0	76
	Married	27	24.0	100.0
Education Background	Senior High School	2	1.7	1.7
	Undergraduate	80	69.6	69.6
	Master	29	25.2	94.8
	Doctor	6	5.2	100.0
Monthly Income	< IDR 5.000.000	48	41.7	41.7
	IDR 5.000.000 - < IDR 7.500.000	23	20.0	61.7
	IDR 7.500.000 - < IDR 10.000.000	17	14.8	76.5
	IDR 10.000.000 - < IDR 12.000.000	9	7.8	84.3
	>IDR 12.000.000	18	15.7	100.0
Working Experience	< 2 years	21	18.2	18.2
	2 - < 4 years	17	14.8	33.0
	4 – < 6 years	8	7.0	40.0
	>6 years	69	60.0	100.0

4.1.2 Common Method Variance

This study implements the procedure of common method variance (CMV) to anticipate and detect the bias response of the questionnaires. The questionnaires were designed anonymous for the respondents who intend to participate in this survey, and the item of the questions was displayed randomly without informing the variable would be responded (Podsakoff, MacKenzie, Lee, & Podsakoff, 2003). Following Eichhorn (2014) this study analysed the response bias from the respondents' answers used Harman's single-factor test and the common latent factor (CLF). The result-clarified variance of the first factor is 34.46%, which is less than 50.00%. Furthermore, the CLF factor loading was .25, which pointed to a 06.25% variance of CMV.

4.1.3 Confirmatory Factor Analysis (Cfa)

The analysis of the measurement model followed the recommendation of Anderson and Gerbing (1988) with a two-step approach comprised of confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and structural equation modelling (SEM). This study employed CFA to analyse the measurement model and estimate the reliabilities and validities of the constructs. Then, SEM was used to validate the hypotheses related to the relationships among the research constructs.

The result of the analysis showed that the measurement model achieved good model fit, with $\chi^2 = 147.057$, $\chi^2 / (df = 81) = 1.816$, ($p < .001$), good fit index (GFI) = .856; comparative fit index (CFI) = .937, incremental fit index (IFI) = .939, Tucker Lewis index (TLI) = .907, normed fit index (NFI) = .874, and root mean square error of approximation (RMSEA) = .064. The values of CFI, IFI, and TLI surpassed .90 and the values of RMSEA and Standard RMR (.038) were lower than .8 (Hu & Bentler, 1998).

Based on the CFA evaluation, the psychometric properties of each factor were measured by a reflective scale (Anderson & Gerbing, 1988; Bagozzi & Yi, 1988). Moreover, composite reliability (CR) exceeded .70 and the average variance extracted (AVE) was above .50, indicating convergent validity (Hair Jr, Black, Babin, Anderson, & Tatham, 2010). The results of CFA showed values of CR between .866 and .926 and values of AVE from .682 to .799. Table 3 shows the results of the factor loading, CR, and AVE, revealing that the model fulfilled convergent validity.

Table 3: The results of CFA model

Construct	Factor loading	Error Variance	Composite reliability (CR)	Average variance extracted (AVE)
Islamic Work Value				
PI1	.660	.564	.926	.687
PI2	.887	.213		
BE1	.942	.113		
BE2	.670	.551		
PA1	1.095	-.199		
PA2	.602	.638		
Trust to Manager				
TR1	.786	.382	.872	.696
TR2	.773	.402		
TR3	.934	.128		
Commitment to Customer Superior Value				
CM1	.826	.318	.866	.682
CM2	.820	.328		
CM3	.832	.308		
Employee Unethical Behavior				
EM1	.851	.276	.923	.799
EM2	.964	.071		
EM3	.863	.255		

Regarding the evidence of discriminant validity, Fornell and Larcker (1981) suggested that the value of the square root of the average of variance extracted (AVE) in each construct should be higher than the relationship coefficients of the particular construct with other constructs. Our findings showed that the square root of AVE was higher than the correlation of each

construct, indicating the research model achieved adequate discriminant validity. Table 4 shows the correlation matrix of discriminant validity.

Table 4: Correlation matrix of discriminant validity

Construct	IWV	TM	UB	CSV
IWV	.829			
TM	.116	.834		
UB	.045	.598	.894	
CSV	.265	.120	.006	.826

4.1.4 Structural Model

Following Anderson and Gerbing (1988), the second step of analysis of the structural model was to validate the significance of the hypotheses. The results showed $\chi^2 = 154.040$; $\chi^2 / (df = 82) = 1.879$, ($p < .001$); RMSEA (root mean square error of approximation) = .067; GFI (good fit index) = .845; NFI (normed fit index) = .868; IFI (incremental fit index) = .934; TLI (Tucker Lewis index) = .900; and CFI (comparative fit index) = .931. Hu and Bentler (1998) recommended that values of CFI, IFI, and TLI, with good model fit should be close to 1.00 and higher than .90 and the result showed excellent model fit. Furthermore, the RMSEA value in the range between .04 and .10 indicated fit value, while SRMR (Standardized RMR) = .041, also leading to adequate model fit.

The validation of the hypotheses focused on the Islamic work value and commitment to customer superior value. We found that Islamic work value positively and significantly affects trust in manager (Hypothesis 1). Furthermore, Islamic work value negatively and significantly impacts unethical behavior (Hypothesis 2), on the other hand, Islamic work value positively and significantly affects commitment to customer superior value (Hypothesis 3). Finally, trust in manager positively and significantly affects commitment to customer superior value (Hypothesis 4), while employee unethical behavior insignificantly affects commitment to customer superior value (Hypothesis 5). Table 5 shows the details of the hypotheses results.

Table 5: Displayed any details of the hypotheses results.

Hypothesis	Estimate	S.E.	C.R	Result
H1 IWV → TM	.522**	.165	3.161	Supported
H2 IWV → UB	-.405**	.195	-2.074	Supported
H3 IWV → CSV	.605***	.128	4.743	Supported
H4 TM → CSV	.267***	.070	3.791	Supported
H5 UB → CSV	-.048	.049	-.976	Not Supported

Note: * $p \leq .1$ ** $p \leq .05$ and *** $p \leq .001$; IWV = Islamic Work Value; TM = Trust to Manager; UB = Unethical Behavior; CSV = Commitment to Customer Superior Value.

4.2. DISCUSSION

The results of this study confirm that Islamic work value increases commitment to customer superior value. This finding informs that when the employee having a good Islamic value, he or she will have a better commitment to serve the customer with superior value. This finding supports the statement that value-based selling includes three crucial elements thoroughly comprehending customers' business goals, improving an offering to help customers in achieving the goals, and credibly presenting how the offering can support the business customer's profit (Terho et al., 2012). Moreover, the finding of Islamic work value positively and significantly impacts commitment to customer superior value relevant with previous studies from Schwepker and Schultz (2013) that stated a commitment to superior customer value as the personal power to provide superior value to the customer and involves an individual, affective commitment to increase the value offered to the customer.

This study also confirms that Islamic work value positively and significantly affects trust in manager, it means that employee with Islamic value has a high level of beliefs in fairness and integrity of the manager relevant with the statement from (Scott B MacKenzie et al., 2001). This finding proves the proposal from Mayer et al. (1995) that ability, benevolence, and integrity as the antecedents of organizational trust. It is also strengthens the study from Sirdeshmukh et al. (2002) that found operational competence, operational benevolence, and problem-solving orientation positively affect trust in frontline employee behaviour.

This study also confirms the positive effect of trust in manager on the commitment to customer superior value. This finding informed the importance of increasing trust of salespeople in manager to build a better commitment of salesperson to customer superior value. The result of this study proves the positive relationship between trust in the manager and affective organization commitment (Bloemer, Pluymaekers, & Odekerken, 2013; Camgöz & Karapinar, 2016). It also in line with the study conducted by Schwepker Jr (2019) that demonstrated trust in managers positively affects salesperson commitment to superior customer value.

Concerning the relationship between Islamic work value and employee unethical behavior, this study confirms that Islamic work value decreases employee unethical behavior. This finding proves a previous study conducted by Mukred Mohsen (2007) who stated that piety as a part of Islamic work value can be measured objectively from Muslim behavior, the result of this study reported that Islamic work value reduces unethical behavior. It is also in line with the study from Beekun and Badawi (1999) as well as Mukred Mohsen (2007), that argued piety would enhance people to become proactive and to have morality and fairness.

This study fails to predict employee unethical behavior decrease commitment to customer superior value. The result of this study does not agree with the previous study that informs the significant relationship between unethical behavior and employee commitment to perform customer superior value (Schwepker Jr, 2017, 2019). The potential explanation of this insignificant is however, the employee who behave unethically, they may still commit to customer superior value. However, this commitment to customer superior value particularly if it has a benefit for the employee not for the organization.

5. CONCLUSION

This study finds Islamic work value positively and significantly affects trust in manager. Moreover, Islamic work value negatively and significantly impacts employee unethical behavior. Islamic work value also has a positive and significant effect on commitment to customer superior value. Hence, trust in manager positively and significantly affects commitment to customer superior value. Finally, this study can not confirm the influence of employee unethical behavior on commitment to customer superior value.

5.1. Managerial Implication

Based on this finding that Islamic work value positively and significantly impacts trust in manager and commitment to customer superior value. Moreover, Islamic work value negatively and significantly affects employee unethical behavior. Therefore, the manager of Islamic microfinance can implement training and development both formal and informal to build Islamic work value for the employee. The success of building employees to have Islamic work values can increase trust in managers, decrease unethical behavior and increase the commitment of the employee to customer superior value.

5.2. Limitation And Future Research

This study only limited the sample of Islamic microfinance in the area of Semarang City, therefore, broaden the sample of employees of the Islamic microfinance in all the provinces of Indonesia will be more representative. Moreover, this study only focuses on Islamic work values in predicting employee unethical behavior, the future study can adapt another side of Islamic perspective such as religiosity or Islamic work ethics to accomplish employee unethical behavior will be interesting.

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